

A Mathematical Model of Emotion and Future Planning

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Abstract

This paper focuses on the emotion branch of psychology and attempts to construct a mathematical model of emotion. Using discrete time, it comprehensively considers various possible events at each time node. The focus is not only on the present but also on the future. The model is capable of selecting preferable future plans. Applied to the example of college students taking the postgraduate entrance examination, the model yields future plan results that align with the choices of most people. The model is applicable to daily life, can provide suggestions for future planning, and facilitates people's lives.

Keywords: Emotion; Mathematical Model; Future Planning

1. Introduction

This paper selects the branch of emotion in psychology and attempts to construct a mathematical model of emotion, applying it to daily life to provide suggestions for people's future planning choices.

2. Definitions and Explanations of Some Terms

First, this paper studies only a single individual, referred to as Jack. Issues involving multiple individuals or changing subjects are not considered. The research subject is always and exclusively Jack.

Definition 1: Psychological Event: A change in the individual's environment perceived as meaningful, such as a person's behavior, speech, natural phenomena, memories, imaginations, etc. It highly depends on the observer's psychological meaning construction. The psychological event defined here is not persistent; it generally occurs over minutes and can be seen as instantaneous. A psychological event is a psychological unit that can be perceived as a whole by the brain.

Subsequent references to "events" in this paper refer to psychological events. Psychological events need to be distinguished from physical events in the narrow sense of special relativity (i.e., the combination of a point in space and an instant in time). Furthermore, it is emphasized that events occurring at different times are different events, even if they are substantively the same. For example, eating the same food for lunch and dinner are two different events.

For a long-term event, such as a long-term task, during which the individual is generally in a calm state for most of the time, and sub-events that can evoke effective emotions occur at intervals

of at least 10 minutes, the long-term event is not considered a single event. Instead, it is viewed as a collection of discrete sub-events. The total emotion of a long-term event equals the sum of the emotions of its sub-events. If the individual is in a prolonged state of suppression or relaxation during the long-term event, a mood factor can be multiplied by the subjective emotional feeling intensity.

Definition 2: Body State Vector \vec{B} : Used to represent the state of organs or concentrations of chemical substances within the body, such as concentrations of adrenaline, noradrenaline, cortisol, acetylcholine, dopamine, heart rate, etc.:

$$\vec{B}(t) = [B_1(t), B_2(t), \dots, B_n(t)]$$

where each component represents the concentration of a substance or a functional value of an organ.

Explanation 1: Appraisal Theory of Emotion[1]: This is the mainstream view in psychology regarding the cause of emotions, established by Lazarus. The theory posits that emotions are not caused by events themselves but by the individual's appraisal of the events. The individual's appraisal of an event is the cause of emotion. The relationship between the event and the individual determines the emotion. The theory also includes concepts of primary and secondary appraisal. Both types of appraisal are rapid, unconscious, but can be noticed afterwards.

Below, I combine this with modern neuroscience research for extension.

Definition 3: Simple Appraisal and Complex Appraisal: Based on modern neuroscience research, when an individual perceives an event, the individual conducts two types of appraisal. One follows the fast pathway thalamus \rightarrow amygdala[2], bypassing the cerebral cortex, inputting only the vague outline of the event, and then issuing signals to change the body state. This appraisal is termed Simple Appraisal. Simple appraisal is the cause of changes in body state. Simple appraisal acts like a trigger or igniter. The other follows the slow pathway thalamus \rightarrow cerebral cortex \rightarrow prefrontal lobe, primarily responsible for analyzing the relationship between the individual and the event. This is termed Complex Appraisal.

Definition 4: Event Tag: Assume that complex appraisal can yield a value (scalar) representing the relationship between the individual and the event. Let the individual be Jack and the event be A; this value can be denoted as $Tag_{Jack}(A)$. This is equivalent to Jack labeling event A. This value is related to event A itself, Jack's current state, and the relationship between Jack and event A. This value is called the Event Tag.

Since the research subject of this paper is always Jack and remains unchanged, the subscript is omitted. Similarly, all subsequent quantities in this paper pertain to Jack, and their subscripts are omitted. The same event is different for different individuals. Thus, the event tag is denoted as $Tag(A)$ (since event A itself carries the time information t_0 of its occurrence, this value represents Jack's complex appraisal of event A at time t_0 . Jack's state is contained within the time information t_0 , so there is no need to add Jack's state at time t_0 as an independent variable).

Complex appraisal can be further divided into primary and secondary appraisal according to Lazarus's theory[3]. Primary appraisal evaluates along multiple dimensions, including: 1. Is this relevant to me? 2. Is this good or bad? etc. Question 1 determines whether $Tag(A)$ is 0, and question 2 determines whether $Tag(A)$ is positive or negative (positive for good, negative for bad). Primary appraisal yields only the sign of $Tag(A)$. Secondary appraisal evaluates along dimensions including attribution, coping potential, future expectations, etc., yielding the absolute value of $Tag(A)$.

Definition 5: Subjective Emotional Feeling Intensity: Assume there exists a scalar that can describe the subjective emotional feeling evoked by an event. Let the event be A; this scalar is denoted as $EM(A)$ (similarly omitting the subscript).

The event in Definition 5 can be either an event in the external physical world or an event simulated by imagination in the brain.

Definition 6: Feature Vector of Simple Appraisal $\vec{F}(A)$: Let event A occur at time t_0 , then:

$$\vec{F}(A) = \frac{d\vec{B}}{dt} \Big|_{t=t_0}$$

Since simple appraisal does not pass through the cerebral cortex, it relates only to event A itself and Jack's body. If two events have identical content and occur closely in time, and Jack's body has no significant change (e.g., aging or illness), then $\vec{F}(A)$ is the same. Even for two individuals with similar physiques, the feature vectors for events with identical content are approximately the same.

Similar to using acceleration as a measure of interaction in Newton's second law $\vec{F} = m\vec{a}$, here the result of the simple appraisal is used to measure the simple appraisal. It must be emphasized that the feature vector of simple appraisal is not a function of time; it depends only on event A (and the individual) and does not change continuously with time. It can be stated in advance that this paper adopts discrete time.

Below is a brief discussion of simple appraisal for different research subjects.

Let event A occur at time t_0 . Removing the time label from event A yields the matter M (M is the content of event A; adding time constitutes the event. For example, eating a certain food, without specifying the time).

Definition 7: Feature Vector of Matter M (Independent of Research Subject): Assume there exists a feature vector $\vec{F}(M)$ that depends only on the matter M itself. Its components $F_i(M)$ satisfy (if matter M occurs at time t_0):

$$F_i(M) = m_{Jack,i}(t_0) \frac{dB_{Jack,i}}{dt} \Big|_{t=t_0}$$

The vector $\vec{m}_{Jack}(t_0) = [m_{Jack,1}, m_{Jack,2}, \dots, m_{Jack,n}]$ is called the Body State Vector of Jack at time t_0 , representing the proportional response of Jack's various physical indicators to the matter at time t_0 . This vector can be approximated as constant over short time scales. The subscript can be replaced with other names, thus applicable to various individuals.

3. Subjective Emotional Feeling Intensity and Emotional Inertia

Postulate 1: $EM(A) = Tag(A) \cdot \vec{F}(A) \cdot \vec{\omega}$

Here, $\vec{F}(A) \cdot \vec{\omega}$ represents the dot product of vectors, indicating a weighted average of various physical indicators. $\vec{\omega} = [\omega_1, \omega_2, \dots, \omega_n]$ represents the weights for the weighted average. The average of physical indicators can be written as:

$$\sum_{i=1}^n F_i(A) \cdot \omega_i$$

which is consistent with the dot product. The subscript is also omitted in the formula.

Note: Bodily sensation is the foundation of subjective emotional feeling. Research shows that even events simulated by imagination in the brain can cause slight bodily sensations. These sensations are very slight, so the subjective emotional feeling evoked by imagined events is also much smaller than in actual situations. The bodily sensation scalar is derived from the body state change vector. The transformation function from the body state change vector to the bodily sensation contribution of subjective emotional feeling intensity can take different forms. Choosing a weighted average here is just a relatively straightforward approximating assumption. A more general case can be represented by a function b , which is a function mapping a vector to a scalar.

Postulate 1*: $EM(A) = Tag(A) \cdot b(\vec{F}(A))$

From Definition 6, let event A occur at time t_0 . The above two formulas can also be written as:

$$EM(A) = Tag(A) \cdot \frac{d\vec{B}}{dt} \Big|_{t=t_0} \cdot \vec{\omega}$$

$$EM(A) = Tag(A) \cdot b\left(\frac{d\vec{B}}{dt} \Big|_{t=t_0}\right)$$

EM(A) is not a continuous function of time; it relates only to the event (with the research subject unchanged).

Explanation 2: Emotional Inertia: Emotional inertia refers to the phenomenon where the emotional state persists for a period even after the event that caused the subjective emotional feeling has ended. The reason for this phenomenon is that changes in body state are not instantaneous; hormonal and other chemical substances in the body take time to decrease to a level where the individual no longer feels them. Emotional inertia produces an emotional residue from the event.

The rate of decrease in concentrations of hormones and other chemical substances in the body can be approximated by exponential functions, but these substances have different properties, leading to significant differences in their decay rates. They are categorized by decay rate into fast substances (e.g., neurotransmitters, etc., bodily sensation disappears in about 5-10 seconds), medium substances (e.g., adrenaline, noradrenaline, etc., bodily sensation disappears in about 2-3 minutes), and slow substances (e.g., cortisol, etc., subjective sensation disappears in about 4-8 hours). The body state vectors for the above three types of substances are denoted as \vec{B}_{fast} , \vec{B}_{medium} , \vec{B}_{slow} , i.e., $\vec{B} = [\vec{B}_{fast}, \vec{B}_{medium}, \vec{B}_{slow}]$. Similarly for the simple appraisal feature vector and weight vector. The exponential function coefficients are denoted as $\lambda_{fast}, \lambda_{medium}, \lambda_{slow}$.

Definition 8: Time-dependent Emotional Residue Scalar R(A,t):

$$R(A, t) = Tag(A) \cdot (\vec{F}_{fast}(A) \cdot \vec{\omega}_{fast} \cdot e^{-\lambda_{fast}t} + \vec{F}_{medium}(A) \cdot \vec{\omega}_{medium} \cdot e^{-\lambda_{medium}t} + \vec{F}_{slow}(A) \cdot \vec{\omega}_{slow} \cdot e^{-\lambda_{slow}t})$$

Definition 9: Emotional Residue Scalar R(A): Let event A occur at time t_0 , then:

$$R(A) = \int_{t_0}^{+\infty} R(A, t) dt$$

After calculation, we get:

$$R(A) = Tag(A) \cdot (\vec{F}_{fast}(A) \cdot \frac{\vec{\omega}_{fast}}{\lambda_{fast}} + \vec{F}_{medium}(A) \cdot \frac{\vec{\omega}_{medium}}{\lambda_{medium}} + \vec{F}_{slow}(A) \cdot \frac{\vec{\omega}_{slow}}{\lambda_{slow}})$$

Let $\vec{\omega}^* = [\frac{\vec{\omega}_{fast}}{\lambda_{fast}}, \frac{\vec{\omega}_{medium}}{\lambda_{medium}}, \frac{\vec{\omega}_{slow}}{\lambda_{slow}}]$, then $R(A) = Tag(A) \cdot \vec{F}(A) \cdot \vec{\omega}^*$. It can be predicted that

λ_{fast} , λ_{medium} , λ_{slow} are all large numbers, so the emotional residue scalar is relatively small compared to EM(A).

Considering emotional inertia, the subjective emotional feeling intensity is denoted as E(A), $E(A) = EM(A) + R(A)$, then:

$$E(A) = Tag(A) \cdot \vec{F}(A) \cdot \vec{v}$$

where $\vec{v} = \vec{\omega} + \vec{\omega}^* = [(1 + \frac{1}{\lambda_{fast}})\vec{\omega}_{fast}, (1 + \frac{1}{\lambda_{medium}})\vec{\omega}_{medium}, (1 + \frac{1}{\lambda_{slow}})\vec{\omega}_{slow}]$, It can be seen that E

compared to EM is essentially just a change in the weight vector, with no fundamental change.

4. Suggestions After Comprehensive Consideration of Future Events

An individual's life encounters many events. Events that can produce effective subjective emotional feelings are generally sparse, discrete rather than continuous, with an interval of at least an hour between two events. Past events cannot be changed, and future events are not yet determined. The individual's future time is divided into discrete segments, each marked by its starting time, and future time is seen as a series of discrete points, represented as a sequence $[t_1, t_2, \dots, t_m]$, where for any $i, t_{i+1} - t_i = \Delta t$, and Δt is a fixed constant. Each t_i is called a time node.

Definition 10: Future Event Sequence: Denoted as $[A_1, A_2, \dots, A_m]$, where A_i occurs at time t_i . A_i may be \emptyset (indicating nothing happens), an event that produces an effective subjective emotional feeling, or an event whose subjective emotional feeling intensity is approximately 0 (emotionally indifferent from \emptyset).

Definition 11: Probability of Future Event Sequence: For each future event sequence, there is a probability $P[A_1, A_2, \dots, A_m]$. This is Bayesian probability. According to Bayes' formula, it can be written as:

$$P[A_1, A_2, \dots, A_m] = P(A_1 A_2 \dots A_m) \\ = P(A_1)P(A_2|A_1)P(A_3|A_1 A_2) \dots P(A_m|A_1 A_2 \dots A_{m-1})$$

Definition 12: Total Emotion of Future Event Sequence: For each future event sequence, there is a total emotion $E_{total}[A_1, A_2, \dots, A_m]$:

$$E_{total}[A_1, A_2, \dots, A_m] = \sum_{i=1}^m E(A_i)$$

Considering all possible future paths comprehensively, take the average of the total emotion over all future event sequences.

Definition 13: Average Total Emotion:

$$\overline{E_{total}} = \sum_{all\ paths} E_{total}[A_1, A_2, \dots, A_m] \cdot P[A_1, A_2, \dots, A_m]$$

Representing various paths with a table, see Table 1. This table is called the Event Table.

t_1	t_2	t_m
$A_{1,1}$	$A_{2,1}$	$A_{m,1}$
$A_{1,2}$	$A_{2,2}$	$A_{m,2}$
$A_{1,3}$:	:
:	A_{2,k_2}	:
:			...	A_{m,k_m}
A_{1,k_1}				

Table 1 event list

Each grid in the table is connected to all grids in the next time node. Each polyline from time node 1 to m is a future event sequence, called a path. This can also be seen as a matrix.

Events are divided into two types: Type One, events that the individual actively chooses, denoted by B; Type Two, possible outcomes from the external world, denoted by C. Events are denoted by A; an event A is either B or C. In the notation of this paper, if an event uses the letter A, it could be either Type One or Type Two; if B is used, it must be Type One; if C is used, it must be Type Two.

Events at each time node must be of the same type. Each event has multiple conditional probabilities. For event $A_{i,j}$, there is

$$P(A_{i,j}|A_{1,\mu_1}A_{2,\mu_2}\dots A_{i-1,\mu_{i-1}})$$

where each μ_i can take values from 1 to k_i , totaling $k_1 \cdot k_2 \dots k_{i-1}$ conditional probabilities.

For Type Two events, these conditional probabilities are conditional probabilities for each prior scenario. These $k_1 \cdot k_2 \dots k_{i-1}$ conditional probabilities are objective and already determined.

For Type One events, it is different. These events can be chosen by Jack. Jack can actively choose to set the probability of one option at a time node to 1 and the probabilities of other options to 0. Suppose Jack chooses the v -th event $B_{i,v}$ at time t_i , then:

$$P(B_{i,j}|\text{any preceding event sequence}) = \begin{cases} 1, & j = v \\ 0, & j \neq v \end{cases}$$

Definition 14: Future Plan Sequence: Select one event from each Type One time node in the event table to form a future plan sequence, denoted as $[B_1, B_2, \dots]$.

After Jack selects his future plan sequence, i.e., selects a specific event for each time node of Type One, all conditional probabilities for all events in the event table are determined, the probability of each path is determined, and the $\overline{E_{total}}$ for that future plan sequence is also determined. After the future plan sequence is selected, P is determined, and then the normalization condition holds:

$$\sum_{\text{All paths}} P[A_1, A_2, \dots, A_m] = 1$$

For an individual, he should, based on all factors he can consider (possible events at each time node), list the event table. For each future plan sequence, calculate $\overline{E_{total}}$, and choose the future plan sequence that maximizes $\overline{E_{total}}$. Of course, he cannot consider all factors; his behavior depends on the factors he considers. Those with short-sightedness act impulsively because they only consider immediate factors, not the future.

According to Zimbardo's Psychology and Life[4], emotion is a special kind of motivation. My understanding is that emotion gives direction to action; the mechanism of seeking pleasure and avoiding pain makes us pursue goals that bring positive emotions and avoid or eliminate goals that bring negative emotions. Emotion may serve as a useful criterion, predicting individual behavior, and providing suggestions to individuals. Therefore, I propose Postulate 2.

Postulate 2: An individual always tends to choose, within all the factors he considers, the future plan sequence that maximizes $\overline{E_{total}}$.

For example, impulsive people act impulsively because they only consider immediate events and not the future. If they considered more long-term, they would not do so. Farsighted people act reasonably because they consider more and farther factors.

Of course, it is impossible to consider all factors, but the more one considers, the more farsighted the individual is, and the result is generally better. Based on Postulate 2, suggestions can be provided to people by more experienced individuals predicting possible future events .

5. Set Theory Representation of Future Events

Definition 15: Matter: A set of the form $\{\emptyset\}$ (representing nothing happens) or $\{\text{a specific matter}\}$ (described in text, without time).

Note: Events in previous sections contain event content and event time. Events occurring at different times, even with the same content, are different events (e.g., eating the same food at noon

and at night). A matter is the content of an event, obtained by removing the time label from an event.

Definition 16: Time Set T: $T = \{t_1, t_2, \dots, t_m\}$, representing future time nodes.

Definition 17: Whole Matter Set ET: There are two construction methods for ET. The first method: Select a large number of matters sufficient to cover most situations in daily life (about tens of thousands, can be classified by type first) to form a finite set.

$$ET = \{M_1, M_2, \dots, M_\eta\}$$

The second construction method: ET is a countably infinite set. There are over 100,000 Chinese characters, but using 3500 characters is sufficient to cover daily expressions. Adding punctuation and symbols, 3600 are selected. Number them sequentially 1-3600. If the text description of a matter is $a_1 a_2 \dots$, use an ordered pair $[a_1, a_2, \dots]$ (an ordered pair is a type of set), where a_1, a_2, \dots are the numbers corresponding to the Chinese characters. Sort all matters according to the following rules:

1. $\{\emptyset\}$ is ranked first.
2. The shorter the length, the higher the rank.
3. For the same length, compare numbers from front to back until a difference appears; the one with the smaller number is ranked higher. For example: $\{\emptyset\} < [1] < [2] < \dots < [3600] < [1,1] < [1,2]$.

After sorting, correspond them sequentially with the natural number set excluding 0: $ET = \{M_1, M_2, \dots\}$. According to this rule, each matter M_j has a matter number $N(M_j) = j$. A matter M can also be completely represented by the matter number $N(M)$.

Later, the first construction method is generally used.

Definition 18: Event: An ordered pair (t, M) , where $t \in T, M \in ET$.

Definition 19: Matter Mapping f : f is a mapping from T to ET. $f(t_i) = M_j$, where M_j is the matter happening at time t_i .

In set theory, ordered pairs and mappings are both sets.

Definition 20: Matter Mapping Set \mathcal{F}_f : The set of all mappings from T to ET. T has m elements, ET has η elements, therefore \mathcal{F}_f has η^m elements. Let $u = \eta^m$, then $\mathcal{F}_f = \{f_1, f_2, \dots, f_u\}$ (if ET uses the second construction method, then \mathcal{F}_f is a countably infinite set).

Each f_i can be used to obtain a future event sequence $[(t_1, f(t_1)), (t_2, f(t_2)), \dots, (t_m, f(t_m))]$. Therefore, each f_i represents a path. Define the E_{total} and P of f_i using the future event sequence corresponding to f_i .

Definition 21: E_{total} and P are both mappings from \mathcal{F}_f to R. E is a mapping from $T \times ET$ to R.

$$E_{total}(f_i) = E_{total}[(t_1, f_i(t_1)), (t_2, f_i(t_2)), \dots, (t_m, f_i(t_m))] = \sum_{j=1}^m E((t_j, f_i(t_j)))$$

$$P(f_i) = P[(t_1, f_i(t_1)), (t_2, f_i(t_2)), \dots, (t_m, f_i(t_m))] = P[A_1, A_2, \dots, A_m] \\ = P(A_1)P(A_2|A_1)P(A_3|A_1A_2) \dots P(A_m|A_1A_2 \dots A_{m-1})$$

Where $A_j = (t_j, f_i(t_j)), j = 1, 2, 3, \dots, m$. After the research subject is determined, E is only related to the event itself, and can be called the eigenvalue of the event. After the research subject is determined, the functional form of E_{total} is uniquely determined. Since the research subject of this paper is fixed and always Jack, the functional form of E_{total} is directly determined and fixed. P, however, is not. P is uniquely determined only after Jack's future plan sequence (each item in the future plan sequence is an event, not a matter, and contains time information) is determined (the research subject is always determined as Jack). Each of Jack's future plan sequences uniquely

corresponds to a functional form of P. Jack's numerous future plan sequences all correspond to one functional form of E_{total} .

By Definition 13, $\overline{E_{total}}$ is:

$$\overline{E_{total}} = \sum_{i=1}^u E_{total}(f_i)P(f_i)$$

If using the second construction method for ET, simply replace both η and u with $+\infty$.

In this formula, the matter at each time node includes all matters in the whole matter set, so there will be paths that are completely unrelated or even contradictory, and also very absurd paths. Even the requirement that each time node has only one type of event is broken. The event type for each time node should be selected first. Those very absurd paths, paths that do not match the event type of the time node, have a probability of 0. It can be understood as: we do not say these paths do not exist, but say their probability is 0.

The individual's subjective freedom lies in changing $P(f_i)$ by choosing different future plan sequences (all paths have been considered, regardless of whether the probability is 0, so the individual cannot change the paths; the paths are objectively existing and fixed; only the probabilities can be changed. For example, paths that do not conform to the individual's future plan sequence all have a probability of 0, and paths that do not match the event type of the time node also have a probability of 0), thereby changing $\overline{E_{total}}$. When the individual's future plan sequence is determined, the functional form of P is determined. When the future plan sequence is not yet fixed, P is not yet determined.

This formula is only for the sake of rigorous mathematical definition and is of no use for actual calculation. Actual calculation does not need to consider all matters in the whole matter set.

Multiplying $E_{total}(f_i)$ by the fixed value Δt allows approximation using integrals.

$$E_{total}(f_i) \cdot \Delta t = \sum_{j=1}^m E((t_j, f_i(t_j))) \Delta t = \int_{t_1}^{t_m} E((t, f_i(t))) dt$$

$$\overline{E_{total}} \cdot \Delta t = \sum_{i=1}^u E_{total}(f_i)P(f_i) = \sum_{i=1}^u P(f_i) \int_{t_1}^{t_m} E((t, f_i(t))) dt$$

The P in the formula is a mapping of mappings, and the codomain of f is not numbers, making it difficult to handle. Represent f by its index. Represent the matter represented by $f_i(t)$ by the index of that matter, i.e., if $f_i(t) = M_j$, then redefine $f_i(t) = j$. In this way, each function in the formula is an ordinary function $R \rightarrow R$.

$$E_{total} \cdot \Delta t = \int_{t_1}^{t_m} E((t, f_i(t))) dt$$

$$\overline{E_{total}} \cdot \Delta t = \sum_{i=1}^u P(i) \cdot \int_{t_1}^{t_m} E((t, f_i(t))) dt$$

Changing the upper limit of integration t_m to a variable, then $E_{total}, \overline{E_{total}}$ are both functions of t_m . Differentiating with respect to t_m , we get:

$$\frac{dE_{total}}{dt_m} \cdot \Delta t = E((t_m, f_i(t_m))) = E(A_{i,m}) = \text{Tag}(A_{i,m}) \cdot \vec{F}(A_{i,m}) \cdot \vec{v}$$

$$\frac{d\overline{E_{total}}}{dt_m} \cdot \Delta t = \sum_{i=1}^u P(i) E((t_m, f_i(t_m))) = \sum_{i=1}^u P(i) E(A_{i,m}) = \sum_{i=1}^u P(i) \cdot \text{Tag}(A_{i,m}) \cdot \vec{F}(A_{i,m}) \cdot \vec{v}$$

The above shows that the event $A_{i,m}$ at time t_m (and Jack) determines the rate of change of E_{total} with time; the path average of E for all events at time t_m (and Jack) determines the rate of change of $\overline{E_{total}}$ with time. $A_{i,m}$ represents the event at time t_m on the i -th path; $A_{i,m}$ on different paths may be the same. No matter what the determined function P is, there is normalization $\sum_{i=1}^u P(i)=1$. If $A_{i,m}$ is a Type Two event, then for paths with non-zero probability, $A_{i,m}$ is Jack's option B, then:

$$\frac{d\overline{E_{total}}}{dt_m} \cdot \Delta t = \sum_{i=1}^u P(i) E(A_{i,m}) = \sum_{i=1}^u P(i) E(B) = E(B)$$

Exactly the emotion caused by Jack's option.

Finally, let's organize the mathematical system:

1. Set $T = \{t_1, t_2, \dots, t_m\}$ composed of m numbers, $t_{i+1} - t_i = \Delta t = \text{fixed value}$.
2. Set $ET = \{M_1, M_2, \dots, M_\eta\}$ composed of η matters (sets of the form {text description}).
3. Set $\mathcal{F}_f = \{f_1, f_2, \dots, f_u\}$ composed of all mappings from T to ET.
4. For each research subject, there is a unique mapping $E: T \times ET \rightarrow R$ corresponding to it. For each research subject, there is a unique mapping $E_{total}: \mathcal{F}_f \rightarrow R$ corresponding to it (The research subject of this paper is always Jack, so the mappings E and E_{total} are a determined, unchanged, specific mapping).
5. For each research subject and future plan sequence $[B_1, B_2, \dots] = [(t_{i_1}, M_{j_1}), (t_{i_2}, M_{j_2}), \dots]$ (t_{i_1}, t_{i_2}, \dots can take any value in T, but in order from large to small; M_{j_1}, M_{j_2} can take any value in ET), there is a unique mapping $P: \mathcal{F}_f \rightarrow R$ corresponding to it. (The research subject of this paper is always Jack, so the mapping P is uniquely determined by the future plan sequence).
6. For each future plan sequence, there is a unique mapping $E_{total}: \mathcal{F}_f \rightarrow R$ and a unique mapping $P: \mathcal{F}_f \rightarrow R$ corresponding to it (the research subject is already determined as Jack), therefore there is a unique number $\overline{E_{total}} = \sum_{i=1}^u E_{total}(f_i) P(f_i)$ corresponding to it.
7. After selecting T and ET, \mathcal{F}_f is determined. For each future plan sequence, determine the mappings $E_{total}: \mathcal{F}_f \rightarrow R$ and $P: \mathcal{F}_f \rightarrow R$, thereby determining the $\overline{E_{total}}$ corresponding to the future plan sequence.

6. Example

Jack signs up for the postgraduate entrance exam, and writes the event table, see Table 2. Write the emotion value next to the event (choose losing one yuan and gaining one yuan as unit 1 for comparison).

t_1	t_2	t_3	t_4
Diligent exam preparation for 3 months (-20000)	Spend 20,000 to enroll in a tutoring class (-20000)	Breakup (-20000)	Pass the exam and get accepted (100000)
Leisure and entertainment for 3 months (10000)	Not enroll in a tutoring class (0)	No breakup (0)	Fail to get accepted (-10000)

Table 2 event list of the example

There are 16 paths in total. Time nodes 1 and 2 are Type One events. Among them, leisure and entertainment \rightarrow spending 20k on tutoring is unreasonable; paths containing it have probability 0.

For convenience, use a,b,c,d to represent the first row, and e,f,g,h to represent the second row. There are 12 paths in total. They are: efcd, efch, efgd, efgh, abcd, abch, abgd, abgh, afcd, afch, afgd, afgh (as can be visualized through a decision tree). For convenience of calculation, we simultaneously divide by 10000. The result is shown in Table 3 and Table 4.

	efcd	efch	efgd	efgh	abcd	abch	abgd
E_{total}	9	-2	11	0	4	-7	6
P	$0.3 \cdot 0.01$ = 0.003	$0.3 \cdot 0.99$ = 0.297	$0.7 \cdot 0.01$ = 0.007	$0.7 \cdot 0.99$ = 0.693	$0.7 \cdot 0.6$ = 0.42	$0.7 \cdot 0.4$ = 0.28	$0.3 \cdot 0.6$ = 0.18

Table 3 Probability of each path

abgh	afcd	afch	afgd	afgh
-5	6	-5	8	-3
$0.3 \cdot 0.4 = 0.12$	$0.7 \cdot 0.5 = 0.35$	$0.7 \cdot 0.5 = 0.35$	$0.3 \cdot 0.5 = 0.15$	$0.3 \cdot 0.5 = 0.15$

Table 4 Probability of each path

Each future plan sequence has 4 paths.

After selecting the future plan sequence [ef], the probabilities of the last eight paths are all 0 (in the table, the non-zero probability for this path obtained by choosing the future plan sequence is represented), it can be calculated: $\overline{E_{total}}[ef]=-0.49$.

Similarly, it can be calculated: $\overline{E_{total}}[ab]=0.2$, $\overline{E_{total}}[af]=1.1$.

Therefore, it is suggested that Jack choose [Study diligently for 3 months, Do not sign up for tutoring class].

A more mathematical expression is:

1. Choose $T = \{t_1, t_2, t_3, t_4\}$
2. Choose $ET = \{a, b, c, d, e, f, g, h\}$
3. Each function $f_i: T \rightarrow ET$ can be represented in order by 4 elements of ET, representing the matters corresponding to t_1, t_2, t_3, t_4 , such as aaaa, abcd.
4. For the future plan sequence $[(t_1, e), (t_2, f)]: E_{total}(f_i)$ is obtained by adding the data for each matter in the sequence corresponding to f_i according to Table 2. And $P(f_i)$, $P(efcd)=0.003$, $P(efch)=0.297$, $P(efgd)=0.007$, $P(efgh)=0.693$, other P, such as $P(aaaa)$, $P(abab)$, etc., are all 0. It can be seen that the normalization of P holds.
5. According to the definition of $\overline{E_{total}}$, we get $\overline{E_{total}}[(t_1, e), (t_2, f)]=-0.49$.
6. Other future plan sequences are similar.

Summarize the steps of the method:

1. Determine the event type for each time node.
2. Write the event table.
3. Determine the functional form of E.
4. Choose a future plan sequence. For each future plan sequence, determine the functional form of P, and calculate the $\overline{E_{total}}$ corresponding to that future plan sequence.
5. Compare the $\overline{E_{total}}$ of different future plan sequences, select the largest one, and the corresponding future plan sequence is the future plan tendency.

7. Summary

Summarize the theoretical system of this paper with a table, see Table 5:

Cause	Result
Individual's appraisal of an event	Produces subjective emotional feeling $EM(A)$ (not directly measurable)
Simple Appraisal	Changes body state (directly measurable)
Complex Appraisal	Produces event tag $Tag(A)$ (not directly measurable)
Emotional Inertia (Body State Inertia)	Produces emotional residue $R(A)$ (not directly measurable)
Comprehensive consideration of all future situations	Select the future plan sequence that maximizes $\overline{E_{total}}$

Table 5 conclusion

References:

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4. Zimbardo, P. G., Johnson, R. L., & McCann, V. Psychology and Life (19th ed.). Boston: Pearson, 2017.